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THE MAIN TASKS OF THE OPERATION OF GAS CELL

M.D.Uzboyev

Annotation is a complex technology complex of gas distribution and gas use systems designed to provide consumers with natural and liquefied uglivodorol gases and to use these gases as fuel.

The main task of the operation of gas hojalig is to ensure the continuous supply of the amount of gas provided by the contracts for the supply of gas from natural gas suppliers to consumers and the use of gas with betalofat and economy.

The operation of gas supply systems of cities and settlements, as well as all types of gas heaters located in them, is carried out by special gas supply organizations. These organizations carry out work on the basis of technological measures to ensure safe and reliable operation of gas networks and its equipment and internal gas equipment of buildings, on the basis of the organization and implementation of planned preventive repair, construction and reconstruction of gas networks and its facilities, the development of gas networks and gasification and ensuring compliance with safety rules and norms in the field of gasGaz hujaligining texnologik majmui quyidagilarni tashkil etadi.

- The urban gas supply scheme (1.1. image);
- External (underground, terrestrial, airborne) Gas Networks laid in the regions of cities and other settlements:
- Facilities and equipment installed in gas networks:

1.1. image. Urban gas supply scheme.

- Gas pipeline electro chemical protection tools:
- Gas control points and gas control devices:
 - Internal gas pipelines of the enterprise and all other types of buildings, equipment and equipment using gas, heating boilers and other:
 - Reservoirs and cylinders of liquefied hydrocarbon gases.

Ensuring compliance with safety regulations in the use of gas is entrusted to gas users in all types of gasified (natural gas, SUG) enterprises and residents ' households. From all types of organizations that use gas, gas utilities require compliance with the following safety and operating rules.

- Rules for the technical operation of gas networks and its equipment and equipment of base-type organizations that use gas as fuel:
 - Rules for the technical service of internal gas networks and equipment of all types of buildings and structures:

The operation of the gas industry facilities of enterprises and organizations is carried out by enterprises and organizations, but the work carried out is carried out in accordance with the agreement with the regional gas supply enterprises or is carried out by the Regional Gas Supply Enterprise on a contract basis.

It is carried out by the Engineer Technical Officer of the gas supply enterprise, which is qualified for operation in order to carry out various “gas hazardous” work, and employees who are allowed to perform “gas hazardous” work. In addition, the gas supply is regularly provided to the employees of the engineering technical staff of the enterprise, technical seminars and practical training are taken.

The main task of the technical operation of gas cell is to ensure the use of gas by all types of consumers without their own, betalofat and economy.

By technical exploitation:

- Ensuring the working condition of all types of gas pipelines.
- Supply of gas in moderation to gas combustion equipment and equipment and activate the organization of normal combustion.
- Acceptance and commissioning of gas pipelines and equipment that are being restarted after a new construction or renovation.
- Strict compliance with the implementation of the state committee” UzSanoatkontexnazorat " and other security rules.

The operation of the gas cell is subject to regular control due to its specificity, and this control is carried out by the enspection of the state committee “UzSanoatkontexnazorat” on the basis of “safety rules in the gas cell”.

LITERATURE USED

1. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 24.09.2020 PQ-4890 “on additional measures for the implementation of an automated system of Natural Gas Control and accounting.

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2. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 6010 “on measures for the sale of Natural Gas and electricity” dated 18.06.
3. Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 22 on approval of the “rules for the use of Natural Gas” of January 12, 2018.
4. “Safety rules of the gas industry” approved by Gosgortehnadzor of Russia on December 26, 1990